

ORBIS

SMART EYES OVER MEDITERRANEAN WATERS

Optimized Real-time maritime Border Surveillance with Intelligent satellite-drone Systems

ORBIS will deliver a next-generation integrated satellite - UAV system for maritime domain awareness and coastal security. Designed for harsh sea environments, it will facilitate autonomous vessel-based operations, long-range monitoring, and real-time AI-enabled detection of distressed vessels and illegal activity. ORBIS represents a European first - an intelligent, holistic maritime-operational system that brings space-to-sea coordination to a new technological frontier.

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